

**PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL
FOUNDATIONS OF SOCIAL SKILLS
DEVELOPMENT BASED ON INTRODUCING
PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS TO WORKS OF ART**

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Annotation: The article discusses the development of social skills by introducing primary school students to artistic works, and for this, first of all, to awaken the imagination of primary school students about the story, the means and methods of education in youth education.

Key words: Story, work of art, text, education. national values, creative, literary, social skills, creative activity.

In the reading classes of primary classes, works of different genres are read and studied, although not scientifically, but practically. Reading textbooks mainly include stories, poems, fairy tales, proverbs, epics, narratives, and riddles. Apart from these, popular scientific works are also taught.

Artistic works of different genres have their own characteristics in terms of construction and style, and their impact on students is also different. Naturally, the text of each genre has its own linguistic features. For example, the text of poetic works is fundamentally different from the text of a story, the text of a fairy tale from the text of a poem, the text of a popular scientific article from the text of works belonging to the parable genre. Riddles are mastered by comparing the similarities between objects and events, while the content of proverbs requires interpretation by means of real life examples. Accordingly, when reading works of art of different genres, the teacher is required to choose appropriate methods.

Methodology of reading a fairy tale One of the reasons why the genre of fairy tales in folklore is well accepted and read by children is the impressiveness, sharpness, meaning and closeness of the language of fairy tales. In most fairy tales,

the image of real life is combined with elements of adventure. The sharp and interesting plot of the fairy tale, the extraordinarily wonderful situation in the development of the story fascinates children, the brave, strong, resourceful, brave, agile characters, the ideological direction of the fairy tale, the constant victory of the power of goodness - goodness in it attracts children. pulls The form of storytelling adopted in a fairy tale is repetition of the same words and phrases over and over again, melodiousness, impressiveness of the language, vividness of means of expression, and great interest for children. Participants in fairy tales are often compassionate, generous, fair, and their opposites, evil, miserly, and greedy characters. The pedagogical value of the fairy tale is that the students are happy that the truth and honesty won in it, that the poor people got out of trouble, that is, that goodness and goodness came true, and that evil and evil were condemned. They always want it to be like this in life. For example, in the fairy tale "Honesty" (3rd grade) the main idea is to help the poor, to live by one's own work, and the idea that this is even the desire of the whole nation is put forward, while "The Punishment of the Trickster" » in the fairy tale (4th grade) the idea that the truth of the simple-minded will win over the tricks of the trickster, and that betrayal will not go unpunished is put forward. Both tales end with the victory of righteousness. This kind of victory is expressed in fairy tales as well as in fairy tales. The fairy tale encourages children to discuss the behavior of the heroes and develop the ability to evaluate, as well as the belief that good always wins. In the process of analyzing the story, the students asked, "What qualities did you like in people?" (or didn't like it?", "Why?", "... why was he punished? (or encouraged?)", "Why are some characters in fairy tales helped even by the forces of nature? (or does he turn away from some of them?)" they observe, discuss and come to a conclusion in the process of finding answers to such questions. In primary grades, stories about animals are taught more often. "About the wolf being a doctor fairy tales" (Anvar Obidjon), "Fox with a jug", "Olapar, Mosh, Musicha" are taught and analyzed in the style of real life stories. When working on the text of a fairy tale, the following types of work are

used: selective reading, answering questions, students themselves creating and answering questions about the content of the fairy tale, making a plan, retelling, creative continuation, telling a story, graphically depicting the characters. In such tales, the habits of animals are analyzed, but it is not recommended to compare them with the character of people. It is known from school experience that young children know well that animals in fairy tales do not speak, foxes and cranes do not visit each other's homes, but they perceive the world of fairy tales as a real life story. When reading and analyzing a fairy tale, all work is directed to a good understanding of its content, the development of the plot, the behavior of the participating characters, and their mutual relations. In this, selective reading and retelling are of great importance. For example, "Is it easy to be polite?" The following tasks can be used to learn the content of (A. Obidjon's) fairy tale:

1. Read the mouse's conversation with his mother. The mouse's "What to do to be polite?" tell how his mother answered his question.
2. Find and read the scene where the Mouse meets the Cat. Why does the evil in Shum Barak's eyes suddenly disappear?
3. Why does the Goat pray to the Mouse "Don't be short"? Find this place and read it.

At the final stage of the analysis of the fairy tale, "Find and read a part of the fairy tale that you really liked", "Tell me why you liked this particular part", "Have there been any events in your life similar to the events in the fairy tale?" with the help of questions like In addition to fairy tales about animals, primary school students also read folk tales such as "The State", "Ilm Afzal", "The Punishment of the Trickster", "A person without skills is close to death". People tell their lives in such tales, that's why after reading the fairy tale, the students will learn about the life of the people in the past, their thoughts and dreams. The analysis of such tales is organized in the style of an artistic story. Under the guidance of the teacher, children evaluate the behavior and certain actions of the participants in the fairy tale, tell their relationship to each other, draw conclusions about some characters based on this,

draw up a fairy tale plan, and read the fairy tale in roles. The fairy tale "State" (grade 4) is a fairy tale describing events related to ordinary life. To prepare for reading a fairy tale, a conversation is held about how our ancestors imagined the environment, nature, and existence. Such a conversation helps to correctly understand the artistic characters in the fairy tale, their mutual relations, behaviors, and characters. In the process of working on the text of the fairy tale "The State", students asked questions such as "How does the peasant's household live?", "Why does the State not want to leave the peasant's household?" by finding answers to questions like When working on a fairy tale, it is important to teach children not only to read a fairy tale, but also to tell it. Telling stories develops oral speech, enriches children's speech with new words and phrases. In order to teach students to freely use the language of fairy tales in the 1st grade, the teacher can tell it during the first introduction to the fairy tale. After the student has mastered the content of the fairy tale, it is necessary to pay special attention to working on his language. When retelling the content of the fairy tale and describing the characters, students are required to use language tools appropriately in their speech. It is necessary to create a demand and a situation, a need for the use of language tools. There are words and phrases in fairy tale language that have a special effect on a child. For example, in the fairy tale "Tiger, Fox and Wolf" "May the mountain goat be yours", "May the rabbit be our king's morning breakfast", "Deer your evening meal, sheep your lunch". students pay attention to the highlighted words in sentences such as when giving, it is necessary to get them to use them in speech. It is necessary to work on the proverbs presented in fairy tales, convey the ideas presented in them to the minds of children, develop communicative speech through memorization, and increase the effectiveness of speech. For example, in the fairy tale "Honest Boy" (1st grade), it is told that the boy won the king's favor with his honesty. The conclusion corresponding to the idea of the fairy tale is expressed by the proverb "Speak the truth even if a sword comes to your head." If the students understand the content of this proverb, they can make up and tell a story like the one above. One way to work on word meanings that is suitable

for elementary school students is to use pictures. For example, in the 2nd grade fairy tale "Kongilchan Otinchi", the names of trees such as birch, oak, shumtol, maple, zirk, togterak, karagay, karaghoch, sycamore are given. A child cannot imagine them. Before reading the fairy tale, it is necessary to show the pictures of this tree, explain its characteristics and name it. After that, a didactic game will be held. In this, tree pictures are distributed to children. Each student will have to say the name of the tree in the picture given to him and tell the word of this tree in the fairy tale in his own words. After reading this tale and being introduced to its content, the students get ready and ask the meaning of the words sharbat, good work, khivchin, and muhayyo in front of them. The answers are filled in and summarized. In the process of working with the text of the fairy tale, it is also important to work on the artistic tools used in it: animation, metaphor, exaggeration. Taking into account all the above points, the construction of fairy tale lessons can be as follows:

1. Introducing the fairy tale: a) preparing students to understand the fairy tale; b) the teacher's expressive reading of a fairy tale, retelling, etc.
2. Conducting a short conversation in order to determine to what extent the students perceived the fairy tale;
3. Read and analyze the fairy tale in parts; some visual aids in it, finding synonyms, dictionary work (explaining the meaning of some words);
4. Preparing to tell a story (reading inside);
5. Telling the tale;
6. Summarizing conversation (opening the idea of a fairy tale);
7. Re-reading a fairy tale with a specific task (creative and independent works);
8. Task verification and completion;
9. Preparing to read (or tell) a fairy tale at home

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of questions created by students in the explanation of the content of an artistic work gives more results. It creates animation and motivation in the classroom. However, it is known from school experience that the ability and level of intelligence of students are not the same. This difference

differs in the formation of motivation for their educational activities. To realize the purpose of the lesson, it is necessary to use various pedagogical methods that arouse interest in students. In particular, creating a scenario based on the story, entering the image, memorizing the dialogic speech and performing it live will bring the spirit of the work to life. Even the slow learners in the class will not be indifferent to the live performance. They are impressed by the action of their comrades and the events of the play unfolding before their eyes. As a result, even if they are mistaken in the details, they understand the idea of the work correctly.

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